

Pat_Number	Age	STA_pa	unspecific_STA_pa	STA_lateral	Alg_CVSG_admission	max_CVSG	CVSG_1.spamsolysis	STA_CVSG
11	49	1	0	0	2	2	2	2
18	39	0	0	0	0	2	2	2
28	54	0	0	2	0	2	2	2
34	31	1	0	2	0	3	3	3
42	49	1	1	1	1	3		1
15	29	1	0	2	3	3	3	3
50	57	0	0	0	1	3	3	3
29	43	1	0	1	0	2	2	2
44	38	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
9	49	1	0	0	0	2	2	2
24	57	0	0	2	0	2	2	2
36	32	1	0	0	0	3	3	3
6	50	0	0	1	0	3	3	3
7	56	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
10	55	1	0	2	2	3	3	3
1	79	0	0	1	0	2	1	2
20	31	1	0	1	0	3	2	3
40	45	1	0	0	1	2	1	1
30	35	1	0	1	3	3	3	3
41	41	1	1	1	0	3	3	0
31	52	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
46	33	1	0	2	0	2	1	2
49	55	1	0	1	2	3	2	3
39	77	1	0	2	0	1	1	1
2	48	0	0	0	2	2	2	2
25	39	1	0	1	3	3	3	3
23	54	1	1	2	1	3	3	1
5	75	1	0	0	0	3	3	3
21	59	1	0	2	2	2	2	2
35	47	0	0	1	0	3	2	3
32	60	1	0	2	1	1	1	1
14	55	1	0	2	0	2	2	2
33	62	1	0	2	1	2	2	2
8	54	0	0	2	1	3	2	3
13	39	1	0	2	0	2	2	2
3	43	1	0	2	3	3	3	3
4	60	1	0	1	3	3	3	3
17	47	1	0	2	0	2	2	2
16	68	0	0	2	2	2	2	2
12	52	1	0	2	1	3	3	3
19	40	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
26	47	1	0	0	0	3	3	3
45	48	1	0	2	1	2	2	2

Intervall_1.spasmolysis_SAT	Intervall_SAH_STA_pa	DNA_pa	unspezifc_DNA	Intervall_SAH_DNA	DNA_CVSG	AFA_lateral	AFA_pa	unspezifc_AFA
8	8	1	0	8	2	1	1	0
15		0	0		2	0	0	0
7		1	0	2	2	1	1	0
11	6	1	1	6	0	1	1	0
11	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
7	7	1	0	7	3	2		2
7		0	0		3	1	1	1
5	8	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
11	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
13	1	0	0		2	1	1	0
7		1	1	3	0	2		2
7	8	1	0	7	3	0	0	0
21		1	0	19	3	1	1	1
9		1	1	9	0	1	1	0
12	12	1	0	4	2	1	1	0
7		0	0		2	0	0	0
5	7	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
6	6	1	0	6	1	1	1	0
		1	0		3	1	1	0
9	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
6	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
6	8	1	0	6	1	1	1	0
3	3	1	0	3	2	1	1	0
6	0	1	1	0	0	2		2
4		0	0		2	0	0	0
4	4	1	0	4	3	1	1	0
8	4	1	1	4	1	0		0
13	13	1	0	13	3	1	1	0
7	7	1	0	7	2	1	1	1
8		1	0	9	3	1	1	0
11	11	1	0	11	1	1	1	0
7	9	1	0	7	2	2		2
10	10	1	0	10	2	2		2
6		0	0		3	1	1	1
6	6	0	0		2	1	1	1
10	10	1	0	10	3	2		2
10	11	1	1	3	3	1	1	0
11	11	1	1	2	0	1	1	0
6		0	0		2	1	1	0
6	6	1	1	0	1	2		2
7		1	0	7	1	1	1	0
8	9	1	0	8	3	1	1	0
5	6	1	0	10	2	1	1	0

AFA_CVSG	Intervall_SAH_AFC	unspecific_STA_lateral	Sex	Group_Outcome	CVSG_Admission	Outcome	Complications	Cerbral_complications
2	8	0	0	1	2	0	1	0
2		0	1	1	0	0	0	2
2	9	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
3	12	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3		2	0	1	3	1	0	3
1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	2
0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	2
0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	2
2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
2		0	1	1	0	1	0	0
3		0	1	1	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
2	11	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
2	4	0	0	1	2	1	0	0
2		0	1	1	0	2	0	0
3	6	0	1	1	0	3	1	1
2	10	0	1	1	0	3	0	2
3		0	1	1	3	3	0	2
0	0	0	1	1	0	3	0	0
0	0	0	0	2	0	4	1	2
2	7	0	1	2	0	4	1	1
2	3	0	0	2	2	4	1	1
1		2	1	2	0	4	1	1
2		0	0	2	2	4	1	0
3	5	0	1	2	3	4	0	3
3		0	1	2	1	4	0	2
3	13	0	1	2	0	4	0	0
2	7	0	1	2	2	5	1	2
3	9	0	1	2	0	5	1	1
1	11	0	0	2	1	5	1	1
2		2	1	2	0	5	1	1
2		2	1	2	1	5	1	1
1	0	0	1	2	1	5	1	1
0	0	0	1	2	0	5	1	0
3		2	0	2	1	5	1	0
3	11	1	0	2	2	5	1	0
2	13	0	0	2	0	5	1	0
2	6	0	1	2	2	6	1	1
3		2	1	2	2	6	1	0
1	7	0	0	2	0	6	1	0
3	8	0	0	2	0	6	1	0
2	5	0	1	2	1	6	0	0

EAVS	AV	secondary_finding	DCI_infarctions	Infarction_pattern	Areas	DCI	laterality	CVSG_leptomeningeal
0	3	0	1	2	1	1	1	2
0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	3	0	1	1	1	1	1	3
1	1	0	2	2	1	1	1	2
1	3	0	7	2	1	1	1	2
1	2	0	1	2	1	1	1	2
0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	5	0	2	2	2	1	2	2
0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	1	0	2	2	1	1	1	3
0	1	0	1	2	2	1	2	2
	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	2	0	2	1	1	1	1	3
	2	0	11	2	2	1	1	2
	1	0	10	4	3	1	3	3
	3	0	1	2	2	1	2	2
	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	1	0	6	2	4	1	2	3
0	3	3	11	2	2	1	3	2
0	3	0	2	2	1	1	1	2
	1	0	2	2	2	1	2	2
0	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	3	7	2	2	1	1	3
	5	0	7	1	1	1	1	3
	3	0	1	3	1	1	1	2
0	0	1	12	3	4	1	3	1
	4	3	5	3	3	1	2	2
0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	2	3	7	2	3	1	3	2
	1	3		0	0	0	0	2
1	3	4	1	3	1	1	1	3
0	2	3	9	2	3	1	2	2
1	6	3	10	4	4	1	1	3
1	5	3	1	2	1	1	1	3
0	3	3	5	3	2	1	1	2
1	3	0	1	2	1	1	1	3
0	7	0	12	3	4	1	3	3
1	7	3	8	3	6	1	5	3
	4	3	8	3	6	1	5	3
1	3	0	8	3	4	1	2	2

leptomeningeal	Perfusionsdefizit	Side_vasospasm	Infarkt_admission	Infarkt_postinterventionell	Number_spasmodolysis	Abstand_SAB_STA_lateral	CVSG_vertebrobasilar	Treatment
0	1 1		0	0	4		0	1
0	1 2		1	0	1		2	1
1	0 1		3	3	5		2	1
1	1 1		3	1	2		0	2
1	1 2		1	0	9	0	0	1
0	2 1		2	2	1		0	5
0	2 2		1	0	1		0	1
0	1 2		1	0	11	11	2	1
0	0 1		0	0	1	0	0	1
1	1 2		0	0	5		0	1
0	2 1		0	0	1		2	1
1	1 1		0	0	7		1	1
0	2 2		0	0	4	0	1	1
0	0 1		0	0	2		0	1
1	0 2		0	0	1		0	1
0	1 1		0	0	7	13	0	1
2	2 2		2	1	8	6	0	1
0	2 1		0	1	4		0	3
1	0 2		1	0	2		1	1
0	1 2		0	0	12	11	0	1
0	2 1		1	0	2		0	1
0	2 2		0	3	6		0	2
1	0 1		3	0	2	5	0	1
1	1 1		3	0	2		0	1
0	2 2		0	1	5		0	1
0	1 1		2	2	3	5	0	1
0	1 2		1	0	2		0	1
1	1 1		0	0	2		1	0
1	2 1		1	0	4		0	1
0	1 2		3	3	7	9	0	3
0	2 1		3	1	1		2	3
1	0 2		1	0	9		1	1
1	2 2		3	0	6		1	2
1	2 2		0	3	14		0	1
0	2 1		1	0	3		0	1
2	1 1		0	1	3		1	1
0	2 1		0	0	6	3	0	1
0	0 1		0	0	3		2	1
0	1 1		3	0	4		2	2
1	1 2		0	0	1		0	1
0	0 1		0	0	1	7	0	1
1	1 1		0	0	5		2	1
0	0 2		0	1	10		1	2

Clinical_worsening	Indication_spasmolysis	Infarction_pre	Infarction_post	Fisher	HH	ETA	TCD	BEHAVIOR
1	2	0	1	2	1	0	1	
1	2	2	1	4	3	0	1	3
1	1	0	0	3	3	0	0	2
0	1	0	1	4	5	1	1	6
1	2	1	0	4	2	1	1	5
1	3	1	0	3	3	1	0	
0	1	0	1	4	4	1	1	7
0	1	0	0	4	3	1	1	5
1	2	0	0	3	2	0	0	
0	1	0	1	4	4	1	1	4
1	2	0	0	4	4	1	1	5
1	1	0	1	4	4	1	1	6
1	2	0	1	3	2	0	0	8
1	2	0	2	3	3	0	0	
1	2	1	2	4	2	0	2	
1	3	1	0	3	3	0	0	
1	1	0	1	4	2	1	1	
1	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	
1	2	0	0	4	5	1	1	
1	2	0	1	4	2	1	1	5
1	1	0	1	3	3	1	1	5
0	1	0	0	4	4	1	1	6
0	1	1	0	4	3	1	1	
1	3	0	1	4	3	1	2	4
0	1	0	1	4	5	1	1	6
1	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	
1	3	0	1	4	1	1	1	
1	2	0	1	4	5	1	0	7
1	1	0	1	4	1	1	0	
0	1	0	0	4	3	1	1	6
0	1	0	0	4	5	1	1	10
1	1	0	1	4	4	1	1	7
1	1	0	1	4	3	1	1	
1	2	0	0	3	2	1	1	8
0	1	0	1	4	5	1	1	7
0	3	1	1	4	3	1	1	5
1	3	0	1	4	5	1	0	10
1	2	0	1	2	2	1	1	4
0	1	0	1	4	5	1	1	10
0	1	1	2	4	3	1	1	8
1	3	1	1	3	2	1	0	5
1	3	1	1	4	4	1	2	
1	2	0	1	4	2	1	1	5

Group_of_Behaviour	Group_of_Drug	EVD	Intervall_Admission_SAH
	2	0	∞
2	1	1	0
1	5	1	2
2	2	1	0
2	1	1	0
	3	0	7
3	3	1	0
2	5	1	0
	2	0	0
2	2	1	1
2	0	1	3
2	1	1	0
3	2	1	0
	2	0	1
	2	0	4
	2	0	0
	0	0	0
	5	1	6
	5	1	
2	5	1	0
2	5	1	0
2	3	1	0
	3	1	
2	1	1	0
2	2	1	0
	0	0	4
	3	1	7
3	2	1	1
	0	1	7
2	3	1	0
3	0	1	0
3	1	1	0
	3	1	9
3	2	1	0
3	1	1	0
2	2	1	1
3	2	1	3
2	1	1	2
3	1	1	0
3	2	1	0
2	1	1	2
	0	0	0
2	3	1	0